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The aryl hydrocarbon receptor (Ahr) is modulated during cellular senescence.

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Cellular senescence was characterized by transcriptional modulation of the aryl hydrocarbon receptor (*Ahr*), which supported a tolerogenic role for otherwise immunologically-restricted factors like IL-32 during senescence in cells of non-hematopoietic origin.

Results

We measured total transcription using an *in vitro* model of senescence, with fibroblasts isolated from children and from elderly humans to define the human senescence program, in an unbiased fashion, by comparing total transcription in young fibroblasts and aged fibroblasts.

Figure 1: Activation of Ahr is an essential component of the senescence program.

GSE262932

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
57491	5.23E-27	0.183	-10.7614612	-1.969825	3188.47	AHRR	351/17001	97.9
196	1.25E-14	0.179	-7.7108459	-1.38183	3520.65	AHR	810/17001	88.4

Ahr activation was a defining element of the senescence gene signature (**Figure 1**).

To validate a role for Ahr activation as an essential component of the senescence gene expression signature, we measured total transcription in young and senescent human umbilical vein endothelial (HUVEC) cells. Ahr activation in senescent human cells was a conserved transcriptional feature of senescence in human cells, though the magnitude of Ahr induction in this model was more modest (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2: Activation of Ahr is an essential component of the senescence program.

GSE155680

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
57491	3.41E-08	0.1097	-5.519154	-0.605196	270.87	AHRR	4359/15580	72.0
196	2.25E-05	0.0757	-4.238897	-0.320826	775.99	AHR	5797/15580	62.8

Discussion

We described here that the gene encoding the aryl hydrocarbon receptor, *Ahr*, is transcriptionally activated in the cycling gene expression program known as senescence, and that Ahr induction is an essential component of the senescence program in humans. These data support a model which proposes intrinsic link between cellular senescence and tolerogenic properties of the exhaustion program otherwise understood to be restricted to cells of the immune system.